

BASIC THERMODYNAMICS LABORATORY MANUAL

(Open Educational Resource)

Class : I B.Tech II Semester
Branch : Chemical Engineering

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DEPARTMENT OF CHEMICAL ENGINEERING

Program Outcomes

PO1	Engineering knowledge: Apply the knowledge of mathematics, science, engineering fundamentals, and an engineering specialization to the solution of complex engineering problems.
PO2	Problem analysis: Identify, formulate, review research literature, and analyze complex engineering problems reaching substantiated conclusions using first principles of mathematics, natural sciences, and engineering sciences.
PO3	Design/development of solutions: Design solutions for complex engineering problems and design system components or processes that meet the specified needs with appropriate consideration for the public health and safety, and the cultural, societal, and environmental considerations.
PO4	Conduct investigations of complex problems: Use research-based knowledge and research methods including design of experiments, analysis and interpretation of data, and synthesis of the information to provide valid conclusions.
PO5	Modern tool usage: Create, select, and apply appropriate techniques, resources, and modern engineering and IT tools including prediction and modeling to complex engineering activities with an understanding of the limitations.
PO6	The engineer and society: Apply reasoning informed by the contextual knowledge to assess societal, health, safety, legal and cultural issues and the consequent responsibilities relevant to the professional engineering practice.
PO7	Environment and sustainability: Understand the impact of the professional engineering solutions in societal and environmental contexts, and demonstrate the knowledge of, and need for sustainable development.
PO8	Ethics: Apply ethical principles and commit to professional ethics and responsibilities and norms of the engineering practice.
PO9	Individual and team work: Function effectively as an individual, and as a member or leader in diverse teams, and in multidisciplinary settings.
PO10	Communication: Communicate effectively on complex engineering activities with the engineering community and with society at large, such as, being able to comprehend and write effective reports and design documentation, make effective presentations, and give and receive clear instructions.
PO11	Project management and finance: Demonstrate knowledge and understanding of the engineering and management principles and apply these to one's own work, as a member and leader in a team, to manage projects and in multidisciplinary environments.
PO12	Life-long learning: Recognize the need for, and have the preparation and ability to engage in independent and life-long learning in the broadest context of technological change.

Program Specific Outcomes	
PSO1	Professional Skills: The ability to research, understand and implement computer programs in the areas related to algorithms, system software, multimedia, web design, big data analytics, and networking for efficient analysis and design of computer-based systems of varying complexity.
PSO2	Problem-Solving Skills: The ability to apply standard practices and strategies in software project development using open-ended programming environments to deliver a quality product for business success.
PSO3	Successful Career and Entrepreneurship: The ability to employ modern computer languages, environments, and platforms in creating innovative career paths, to be an entrepreneur, and a zest for higher studies.

Basic Thermodynamics Laboratory

I BTech II Sem

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Course Outcomes: at the end of the semester, the student will be able to :

CO-1	Demonstrate an understanding of the fundamental principles underlying chemical engineering through practical experimentation. To Setup the laboratory equipment according to desired standards and perform experiments while keeping safety precautions and accuracy in view.
CO-2	Show an understanding of the issues related to experimental aspects of chemical engineering.
CO-3	Investigate the different parameters related to experiments and relate the interactions of those parameters with engineering principles.
CO-4	Show management skills related to planning, developing and report writing activities.
CO-5	Demonstrate some understanding of the professional obligations related to the discipline of engineering, with a special emphasis of the development of safe working practices during laboratory exercises

Course Articulation Matrix

Course Outcomes	PO-1	PO-2	PO-3	PO-4	PO-5	PO-6	PO-7	PO-8	PO-9	PO-10	PO-11	PO-12	PSO-1	PSO-2	PSO-3
CO-1	3	3	3	3	2	1	2	2	2	2	0	2	1	1	1
CO-2	3	3	3	2	2	0	1	2	2	2	0	3	3	1	3
CO-3	3	3	3	2	2	1	0	2	3	2	0	3	3	2	3
CO-4	3	3	3	2	1	1	0	1	1	2	0	3	3	1	3
CO-5	3	3	3	2	2	1	0	1	3	2	1	3	3	2	3

Basic Thermodynamics Laboratory

List of Experiments

Cycle – 1	Pg No
1. Heat of solution by solubility method	7
2. Liquid – liquid equilibrium	11
3. Excess property determination	14
4. Experiment based on First law of thermodynamics	17
5. The heat of mixing	20
6. The study of phase change	23
7. Thermodynamics – second law - exam the cooling processes of hot water and validate the second law of thermodynamics	25
 Cycle – 2	
8. Equilibrium constant determination	10
9. Joule's experiment demonstrated the validity of the first law of thermodynamics	28
10. Entropy & Enthalpy Changes	30
11. Using the Ideal Gas Law to Determine the Purity of a Zinc Sample	35
12.. Heat, Temperature and Conduction	45

Chemicals Required

1. Distill water
2. $K_2Cr_2O_7$ crystals
3. KI powder
4. $Na_2S_2O_3$ pellets
5. Iodine solution
6. Ethanol
7. CCl_4 solution
8. Benzene
9. Acetic Acid
10. Methanol
11. Napthalene
12. Candle wax
13. Ammonium Chloride
14. Ammonium Nitrate
15. Calcium Chloride
16. Acetone

EXPERIMENT
ONE

HEAT OF SOLUTION BY SOLUBILITY METHOD
AIM:

1. To determine the solubility of the given solute in the given solvent at different temperatures ranging from 30 °C to 70 °C
2. to plot a graph of solubility against the temperatures.
3. to calculate the heat of solution, by estimating the amount of solute dissolved at various temperatures, using titration against KMnO_4 or Na_2SO_4 as the case may be.

APPARATUS: 500ml beaker, measuring jar, conical flask, burette, pipette, heating mantle, thermometers, specific gravity bottles

CHEMICALS REQUIRED: Distill water, $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ crystals, KI, starch indicator

THEORY:

Variation of the solubility of a substance with temperature is given by

Vant-Hoff's Equation

$$\left(\frac{d(\ln S)}{dT}\right) = \left(\frac{\Delta H^0}{RT^2}\right)$$

S -- Solubility of the substance.

ΔH^0 -- Heat of solution.

R -- Molar gas constant.

T -- Absolute temperature.

Assuming ΔH^0 is constant over a temperature range T_1 to T_2 , we obtain by integration

$$\ln\left(\frac{S_1}{S_2}\right) = \left(\frac{\Delta H^0}{R}\right)\left(\frac{1}{T_2} - \frac{1}{T_1}\right)$$

$$\ln\left(\frac{S_2}{S_1}\right) = \left(\frac{-\Delta H^0}{2.303 R}\right)\left(\frac{T_1 - T_2}{T_1 T_2}\right)$$

SOLUTIONS TO BE PREPARED

1. 10% KI solution.
2. Dilute H_2SO_4
3. 0.1N $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$
4. 1% Starch Indicator

1. 10% KI 100ml solution preparation

- Dissolve 5 gm of KI in 10 ml of distil water.
- Transfer the solution into 100 ml std flask using funnel.
- Add distill water till the meniscus of the flask.

2. Dilute H_2SO_4

Add 10 ml of Concentrated sulfuric acid to 90 ml Distill water.

3. 0.1 N $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ 500ml solution

- Molecular weight of Sodium Thiosulphate is 248.
- By using Normality formula find out the weight of Thiosulphate required for 500 ml solution preparation.
- Add the Thiosulphate to 50 ml of distill water and transfer it to 500ml standard flask using funnel.
- Add the distill water till the meniscus of the standard flask.

4. Starch Indicator solution preparation

- Weigh 1 gm of starch powder
- Dissolve 1 gm in 50 ml of distill water.
- Transfer the solution to 100 ml standard flask using funnel.
- Add Distill water till the meniscus of the standard flask.

PROCEDURE:

- Water is taken in 400 ml beaker and gradually heated, upto 70°C .
- $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ crystals are added slowly with stirring;
- saturated solution is prepared at 70°C .
- The solution is allowed to cool. A known volume of the liquid is pipetted out at a particular temperature [say 65°C] (the solution can be drawn off using a pipette packed with glass wool) in a standard flask, diluted if necessary, and portion of it is acidified with dil H_2SO_4 .
- 10 % KI is added and titrated against saturated solution of $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ using starch as indicator.
- The amount of $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ dissolved at that temperature is estimated .
- The solution in the beaker is allowed to cool further. Another known volume of $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ solution at different temperature (say 60°C) is taken out and the amount is estimated as above.
- The titration is repeated with the same volume of $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ solution at different temperatures say 55°C , 50°C , 45°C , 40°C , and 35°C and the amount is estimated.

Note: The experiment can be employed in the case of determination of heat of solution of benzoic acid, the amount can be estimated with standard NaOH and in the case of Ammonium oxalate, standard KMnO_4 can be used.

MODEL CALCULATIONS:

Determination of solubility at _____ $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

By volumetric principles, $V_1N_1 = V_2N_2$

V_1 = Volume of dichromate solution

N_1 = Normality of dichromate solution.

V_2 = Volume of $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ solution

N_2 = Normality of $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ solution

Equivalent weight of dichromate = 49 g/gm equivalent

Solubility at _____ $^{\circ}\text{C}$ = _____ gm/lit.

Similarly, solubility at _____ $^{\circ}\text{C}$ = _____ gm/lit.

Using Vant – Hoff's equation

$$R = 8.314 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1} = 1.987 \text{ Cal mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$$

$$\Delta H = \text{_____ Cal mol}^{-1}$$

Observation table:

S.No.	Volume of $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ solution (ml)	Temp (t) $^{\circ}\text{C}$	Burette Reading (ml)		Volume of $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ (ml)
			Initial	Final	

Calculation table:

S.No.	Temp (t) $^{\circ}\text{C}$	Temp (T) K	Volume of $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$	Normality of $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ (N1)	Solubility S (g/lit)	ΔH° (Cal/ mole)

Graph: Plot graph S_1 Vs Temp (T)

RESULT:

The heat of solution of the given $K_2Cr_2O_7$ solution by solubility method was found to be _____ Cal / mole.

Result table:

S.No.	Temp (T) K	Solubility S (g/l)	ΔH^0 (Cal/ mole)

EXPERIMENT**TWO**

LIQUID - LIQUID EQUILIBRIUM**AIM:**

To draw the solubility curve and tie – lines for the given ternary system.

APPARATUS: 500ml beaker, measuring jar, conical flask, burette, pipette, heating mantle, thermometers, specific gravity bottles

CHEMICALS REQUIRED: Distil water,

System 1: Nitrobenzene-Acetic acid-Water.

System 2: Benzene-Acetic acid – Water.

PRINCIPLE INVOLVED:

All extraction systems are multicomponent and the simplest systems contains a minimum of three components, a solute, a solvent and diluent. The solute is the material to be extracted from the feed mixture (solute and diluent) using a solvent which must not be completely miscible with the diluent.

If the three components are liquids, then the system can be classified into three types based on the number of partially miscible binaries. Type I system contains only one partially miscible pair as in the Benzene – Acetic acid – Water system. The system n – Heptane – Cyclohexane – Aniline containing two partially miscible binaries is type II system. Type III system containing 3 non – consolute pairs is uncommon, Succinic nitrate – Ether – Water system is an example.

For all 3-component system, the degree of freedom is the composition of components. So carry out the experiment at constant temperature and pressure.

Knowledge of equilibrium properties is of great importance in extraction calculations. It is common practice to use a phase diagram to show the relationship among these equilibrium properties.

This kind of diagram shows two sets of data.

The solubility curve which shows the boundary between the homogeneous and the heterogeneous regions of the system. The portion of the diagram under the solubility curve has two

phases (that is heterogeneous). This equilibrium or solubility curve represents the limiting solubilities.

The equilibrium lines known as tie – lines connect the compositions of the respective co – existing phases or conjugated solution lying on the bi-nodal curve.

CONJUGATED SOLUTION:

If A and B are two components forming a binary mixture, a solution A in B and a solution B in A are formed on stirring, then the solution is said to be conjugated solution.

PROCEDURE:

System 1: Nitrobenzene-Acetic acid-Water.

System 2: Benzene-Acetic acid – Water.

Carry out the experiment at room temperature.

1. Prepare various compositions of binary mixtures (Nitrobenzene-Water) by volume. It forms two layers.
2. Add third component (Acetic acid) dropwise until two layers disappear and forms homogeneous solution. Note the burette reading.
3. The miscibility composition is tabulated.
4. Plot the graph by converting the miscibility composition in terms of weight fraction.
5. Draw the solubility curve.
6. From the graph choose a mixture composition, which lies in the heterogeneous region (portion under solubility curve), and prepare it.
7. Shake it well and allow it to settle. Two layers will be obtained.
8. Remove the extract or raffinate layers and analyze it for any one of the components (solute or solvent). (Here solvent acetic acid is analyzed).
9. Carry out the same analysis of acetic acid by titrating the extract with sodium carbonate Na_2CO_3 .
10. Carry out the same analysis for the other layer.
11. The two ends of the tie line composition are obtained from the above two analyses.
12. Draw the tie line.
13. Similarly, draw another tie line by choosing another heterogeneous composition.

Model graph:

B and C are partially miscible with one another. b_1c_1, b_2c_2 are tie – lines.

Tabular column:

Note down the densities of three components at room temperature.

EXPERIMENT**THREE**

EXCESS PROPERTY DETERMINATION**AIM:**

To determine the partial molar volume and excess molar volume of a non-ideal mixture at atmospheric temperature and pressure.

APPARATUS: 500ml beaker, measuring jar, conical flask, burette, pipette, heating mantle, thermometers, specific gravity bottles

CHEMICALS REQUIRED: Methanol, distil water

PRINCIPLE:

Excess functions are thermodynamic properties of solutions which are in excess of those if an ideal solution at the same temperature, pressure and composition. If M represents the molar value of any extensive thermodynamic property (eg. V, U, H, S, G etc.), then an excess property M^E is defined as the difference between the actual property value of a solution and the value it would have as an ideal solution at the same temperature, pressure and composition.

$$M^E = M - M^{id}$$

If the thermodynamic property is the volume then the excess volume is given by

$$V^E = V_i - V_i^{id}$$

Excess functions may be positive or negative. When the excess property (eg. Volume) of a solution is greater than zero, the solution is said to exhibit positive deviations from ideality whereas if it is less than zero the deviations from ideality are said to be negative. M_i is the pure component molar thermodynamic property of a component forming mixture. For a component in an ideal solution, the partial molar property \bar{M}_i is same as the pure component molar property M_i . If the mixture behaves as non-ideal, then the partial molar property that is formed by mixing two or more components. The components may be ideal and the resulting solution may be ideal or non-ideal. The excess property determination is very much useful in determining the property of mixing and is further used in solution property determination.

PROCEDURE:**SYSTEM: METHANOL – WATER**

- Prepare different compositions of methanol- water mixture by taking methanol (say 1,2,3, . . . 9 ml) and make them to 10 cc by adding water.

- Before mixing , weigh the components individually.
- Shake well. Pipette out 5 cc of mixture into a specific gravity bottle and find its weight.
- Repeat this for other mixtures also.
- Pipette out 5 cc of pure components as well into the specific gravity bottle and find its weight.
- Determine the density of the pure component as well as for the above mixtures; from this calculate specific volume.
- Find the moles of methanol and water. Find the mole fractions.
- The average molecular weight is found by using the formula.

$$\text{Avg.mol.weight.} = (x_1M_1)+(x_2M_2)$$

Where:

x_1, x_2 – mole fraction of components 1 & 2

M_1, M_2 – molecular weights of components 1 & 2

Find the molar volume by multiplying specific volume and average molecular weight of individual mixtures.

A graph of molar volume vs. composition of the methanol is to be drawn. From the graph at different composition (say 0.1, 0.2, . . . , 1.0) determine partial molar property by

TANGENT INTERCEPT METHOD:

At each of the selected liquid compositions find \overline{V}_1^E using the equations.

$$\overline{V}_1^E = \overline{V}_1 - V_1 \quad \text{and}$$

$$\overline{V}_2^E = \overline{V}_2 - V_2$$

Where:

$\overline{V}_1, \overline{V}_2$: partial molar volume of component 1 & 2; at specified x_1, x_2 .

V_1, V_2 : pure component molar volume of 1 & 2.

Find the excess volume of mixture using the formula.

$$V^E = x_1\overline{V}_1^E + x_2\overline{V}_2^E$$

Draw a graph between $V^E, \overline{V}_1^E, \overline{V}_2^E$ and x_1 the composition of methanol. From the graph find the partial molar excess volume at infinite dilution.

RESULT:

At atmospheric temperature and pressure

$$\bar{V}_1^E = \text{_____ cc/mole.}$$

$$\bar{V}_2^E = \text{_____ cc/mole.}$$

TABULATION

TABLE 1:

T= °C, P= 1 atm, methanol-1, water-2, M₁=32 gm /mol, M₂ = 18 gm/mole.

Volume Of Methanol (cc)	Volume Of water (cc)	Weight of methanol (g) w ₁	Weight of water (g) w ₂	Weight of 5 cc of mixture (g) w	n ₁ = $\frac{w_1}{M_1}$	n ₂ = $\frac{w_2}{M_2}$	n= n ₁ +n ₂	X ₁ = $\frac{n_1}{n}$	X ₂ = $\frac{n_2}{n}$
5	0								
0	5								
1	9								

TABLE 2:

Specific volume = 5cc/w gm	Avg. mol. Wt. = (x ₁ M ₁)+(x ₂ M ₂) (gm/gm mole.)	V molar volume =(Specific volume)*avg molecular weight {cc/mole.}

TABLE 3:

V₁= _____ cc/mole., V₂ = _____ cc/mole.

x ₁	x ₂	\bar{V}_1	\bar{V}_2	$V_1^E = \bar{V}_1 - V_1$	$V_2^E = \bar{V}_2 - V_2$	$V^E = x_1V_1^E + x_2V_2^E$

EXPERIMENT**FOUR**

FIRST LAW OF THERMODYNAMICS**AIM:**

To determine the relationship between internal energy, heat and work.

APPARATUS

- i) A pack of popcorn kernels
- ii) Butter @ oil (if desired)
- iii) A small pot with lid
- iv) Thermometer
- v) Plate (steel) as a force
- vi) Steel Ruler
- vii) Stove

PRINCIPLE INVOLVED:

First Law Of Thermodynamics

The first law of thermodynamics is simply a statement of conservation of energy principle and it asserts that total energy is a thermodynamic property. Energy can neither be created nor destroyed; it can only change forms. This principle is based on experimental observations and is known as the First Law of Thermodynamics. The First Law of Thermodynamics can therefore be stated as follows:

When a system undergoes a thermodynamic cycle then the net heat supplied to the system from its surroundings is equal to the net work done by the systems on its surroundings.

$$\Sigma dQ = \Sigma dW$$

where Σ represents the sum of a complete cycle.

Work and Heat Transfer

Work transfer is defined as a product of the force and the distance moved in the direction of the force. When a boundary of a close system moves in the direction of the force acting on it, then the system does work on its surroundings. When the boundary is moved inwards the work is done on the system by its surroundings.

$W = F \times s$ (Nm) where F = force (N) s = distance (m)

Heat is a form of energy which crosses the boundary of a system during a change of state produced by the difference in temperature between the system and its surroundings.

Internal Energy

Internal energy is the sum of all the energies a fluid possesses and stores within itself. The change in internal energy is determined only by the net energy that has been transferred across the boundary and is independent of the form of that energy (work or heat) or the process path of the energy transfer. In molecular simulations, molecules can of course be seen, so the changes occurring as a system gain or loses internal energy are apparent in the changes in the motion of the molecules. It can be observed that the molecules move faster when the internal energy is increased. Internal energy is, therefore, a thermodynamic property of state.

$$dU = dQ - dW$$

$$U_2 - U_1 = Q_{12} - W_{12}$$

Unit : J @ kJ

PROCEDURE:

1. Measured 30 g the popcorn kernels.
2. Pour enough oil to lightly coat the bottom of the pot.
3. Place and smooth the pop corn kernels into the pot.
4. Measure height of the popcorn kernels with a steel ruler. (take a reading)
5. Cover the pot with the lid.
6. Place the pot over low fire and wait for a few seconds to make the pot hot.
7. After a few minutes, what happens to the kernels?
8. Wait for another few minutes for all the kernels to pop. (What do you observe on the lid of the pot?)
9. Once it has slowed down sufficiently, remove the pan from the burner and turn off the stove. Measure a temperature (take a reading).
7. Repeat step 2 to step 6 with 50 g the popcorn kernels.

CALCULATION:

RESULT:

No.	Weight of Popcorn Kernels (g)	Heat [$Q = mC_p (T_2 - T_1)$]kJ/kgK		Work (W kJ)			Internal Energy U (J @ kJ)
		TEMPERATURE T1(°C)	TEMPERATURE T2(°C)	FORCE (N)	DISTANCE S (m)	($W = F \times s$) (Nm @ J)	
1.	30 g						
2.	50 g						

For approximate calculations with air : $C_p = 1.005 \text{ kJ/kgK}$

EXPERIMENT**FIVE**

THE HEAT OF MIXING**AIM:**

To determine the heat released or absorbed when two solvents are mixed

APPARATUS:

500ml beaker, measuring jar, conical flask, burette, pipette, heating mantle, thermometers, specific gravity bottles, Styrofoam coffee cups

CHEMICALS REQUIRED:

Ethanol, Acetonitrile, distill water

THEORY:

There are two factors that can drive processes to occur. The first is the heat exchanged as result of the process. This is referred to as the “change in enthalpy” and sometimes as “the heat of reaction”. If heat is released in the process, it favours the spontaneity of the reaction. The second is the change in the state of order in the system. This is referred to as the “change of entropy”. A process that results in a more disordered state favors spontaneity. These two factors can work together or fight it out in the change in free energy which is a function of the change in enthalpy and the change in entropy. If change in free energy is negative, the reaction occurs, If it is positive, the reaction does not occur. Thus any spontaneous endothermic process has to be driven by a positive change in entropy.

PRINCIPLE INVOLVED:

$$\Delta G = \Delta H - T \Delta S$$

Intermolecular interaction in polar solvents, such as water and ethanol are based on hydrogen bonding. Pure water exists as spheres of 10 – 30 water molecules held together via hydrogen bonds. Pure ethanol is similar, but generally clusters of ethanol are smaller. As we will soon verify, these two solvents are completely miscible in all proportions. What happens to the intermolecular bonding structure when these two solvents are mixed? Some water – water hydrogen bonds and ethanol – ethanol hydrogen bonds are broken and some water – ethanol hydrogen bonds are formed. The process of breaking bonds is endothermic (heat is absorbed by the molecules and the energy is used to break the bonds). The process of making bonds is exothermic (heat is released). By measuring the temperature change of the solutions upon mixing, one can assess whether a net number of hydrogen bonds were formed or broken upon mixing. Because molecules that are on the inside of the sphere are generally involved in more hydrogen bonding than those on the surface of the sphere, an exothermic mixing suggests that bigger clusters were formed and an endothermic mixing suggests that mixing has resulted in smaller solvent clusters.

PROCEDURE:

1. Use nested Styrofoam coffee cups as the calorimeter in this experiment.
2. Whichever solvent is largest in volume in the particular trial you are performing will be measured using a graduated cylinder and poured into the cup.
3. A top of the cup will have a hole in it where you can stick a thermometer.
4. Place the top on and record the initial temperature of the solvent.
5. Measure the solvent to be added using a graduated cylinder designated for this solvent (so to prevent any prior mixing).
6. With the thermometer in place, have one person carefully crack the top open enough to let another person quickly (but carefully) pour the solvent into the cup.
7. The first person should quickly readjust the top on the cup after the solvent is added.
8. Gently stir the mixture.
9. The temperature of the solvent will change fairly rapidly upon mixing and should level out a new temperature after a minute or so.
10. Record the final temperature.

OBSERVATION TABLE**Group 1**

	Vol. of H ₂ O ml	Vol. of EtOH (ml)	Temp (°C)
Trial 1	1	30	
Trial 2	3	22	
Trial 3	7	22	
Trial 4	12	17	
Trial 5	20	7	

Group 2

	Vol. of H ₂ O ml	Vol. of EtOH (ml)	Temp (°C)
Trial 1	2	27	
Trial 2	4	20	
Trial 3	8	18	
Trial 4	15	12	
Trial 5	25	4	

FORMULAE:

Moles = weight/ molecular weight = (density * volume)/ molecular weight

Mole fraction – moles of A/ (moles of A + moles of B)

CALCULATION TABLE:**Group 1**

	Moles of H ₂ O	Moles of EtOH	Mole fraction of H ₂ O	T _i (°C)	T _f (°C)	ΔT = T _f - T _i
Trial 1						
Trial 2						
Trial 3						
Trial 4						
Trial 5						

Group 2

	Moles of H ₂ O	Moles of EtOH	Mole fraction of H ₂ O	T _i (°C)	T _f (°C)	ΔT = T _f - T _i
Trial 1						
Trial 2						
Trial 3						
Trial 4						
Trial 5						

Graph: The graph has to be plotted between ΔT and mole fraction of water in ethanol – water system for both the groups.

RESULT:

EXPERIMENT**SIX**

THE STUDY OF PHASE CHANGE**AIM:**

1. To study the phase change of a substance from liquid to solid by plotting the cooling curve.
2. To determine the melting point of the given substance and to find out the transition time.

APPARATUS:

Heating mantle, thermometer, metal bowl, burette stand, test tube, watch glass, weighing balance.

CHEMICALS REQUIRED:

Napthalene, candle wax

THEORY:

The term change of phase means the same thing as the term change of state. The change of phase always occurs with a change of heat. However, the temperature does not change. When we heat a solid, the energy supplied is used to increase the kinetic energy of its molecules, and thereby its temperature increases. Energy is required to melt a solid, because the cohesive forces between molecules must be partially overcome to allow the molecules to move about. Similarly, energy is required to vaporize a liquid, because in so doing the molecules are separated and molecular attractive forces are overcome. But there is no temperature change until a phase change is complete. i.e., during phase change, the energy supplied is used only to separate the molecules; no part of it is used to increase the kinetic energy of the molecules. So its temperature will not rise, since kinetic energy of molecules remains the same.

The quantity of heat absorbed or released when a substance changes its physical phase at constant temperature (e.g. From solid to liquid at melting point or from liquid to gas at boiling point) is termed as its latent heat. The quantity of heat absorbed or released when unit mass of a substance changes its physical phase at a given temperature is called specific latent heat. The constant temperature at which melting or boiling take place is known as the melting or boiling point.

PROCEDURE:

- The mass m_1 of the empty boiling tube.
- Sample of mass m_2 is put into the boiling tube.
- It is melted by keeping the test tube immersed in hot oil bath. The sample melts into clear liquid.

- When it melted completely, the test tube is taken out, wiped dry, suspended in air and allowed to cool.
- A thermometer immersed into the melt.
- A stopwatch is started and the temperature is noted for every equal interval of time.
- The time – temperature observation is taken till the liquid get frozen into solid and gets cooled to room temperature.
- Draw a cooling curve by taking time along the X – axis and temperature along Y – axis.
- The temperature corresponding to the horizontal region will give the transition temperature.
- The time for the transition time is also noted from the graph. The experiment is repeated for different samples.

OBSERVATIONS:

Mass of the sample, $m_2 =$ _____ kg

Specific heat capacity of glass, $C_1 =$ _____ J/Kg.K

Specific heat capacity of sample, $C_2 =$ _____ J/Kg.K

S.No.	Time in minutes	Temperature in $^{\circ}\text{C}$

Result:

The cooling curve for the phase change of the sample studied.

Transition time of the sample = _____ min

Melting point of the sample = _____ $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

EXPERIMENT**SEVEN**

EXAM THE COOLING PROCESSES OF HOT WATER AND VALIDATE THE SECOND LAW OF THERMODYNAMICS**AIM:**

We will exam the cooling processes of hot water and validate the second law of thermodynamics

APPARATUS:

Heating vessel, Thermometer, Agitator

CHEMICALS REQUIRED:

Water

THEORY & PRINCIPLE:

Entropy is a measure of the numbers of ways the energy can be distributed in a system of particles (molecules, atoms, or ions). Particles in a system at equilibrium have the same average energy. However, at a given instant of time, particle most likely have different amount of energy. One particle may have certain amount of energy at one instant, and at next, it could have more or less. Depends on the energy the particle has, it will able to access different energy levels. The total amount of energy will determine what energy levels are accessible to particles.

Mathematically Ludwig Boltzmann expressed entropy S , as:

$$S = k \ln(W)$$

Where k is the Boltzmann constant = 1.38×10^{-23} J/K. W is the numbers of ways the energy can be distributed in a system of particles

The Second Law of Thermodynamics states that entropy, or the amount of disorder in the universe, increases each time energy is transferred or transformed. Each energy transfer results in a certain amount of energy that is lost— usually in the form of heat— This heat energy can temporarily increase the speed of molecules it encounters. As such, the more energy that a system loses to its surroundings, the less ordered and the more random the surroundings become.

Entropy and the Second Law of Thermodynamics describe a wide range of occurrences in nature and engineering. A refrigerator is essentially a heat pump and removes heat from one location at a

lower temperature, the heat source, and transfers it to another location, the heat sink, at a higher temperature. According to the second law, heat cannot spontaneously flow from a colder location to a hotter one. Thus, work, or energy, is required for refrigeration. A campfire is another example of entropy change in real life. The solid wood used as fuel burns and turns into a disordered pile of ash. In addition, water molecules and carbon dioxide gas are released. The atoms in the vapors spread out in an expanding cloud, with infinite disordered arrangements. Thus, the entropy changes from burning wood is always positive. The released heat from the burning woods heats up the surrounding and makes the entropy of the surroundings increase, therefore, the entropy of the universe increases. That is why burning wood is a spontaneous Process.

Thermodynamic second law can also be demonstrated in a classic food web. Herbivores harvest chemical energy from plants and release heat and carbon dioxide into the environment. Carnivores harvest the chemical energy produced by herbivores—with only a fraction of it representing the original radiant energy from the sun—and also release heat energy with carbon dioxide into their surroundings. As a result, the heat energy and other metabolic by-products released at each stage of the food web have increased its entropy.

Think about gas trapped in a container with known volume, pressure and temperature as the system. The gas molecules can have an enormous number of possible configurations. If the container is opened, the gas molecules escape, and the number of configurations increases dramatically, essentially approaching infinity. If in the gas expansion process, there is no energy exchange between the gas molecules and its surrounding, the system become the universe. Thus, ΔS , or the change in entropy for the universe is greater than zero. Thus, the gas expansion process is spontaneous.

Similarly, entropy also increases when hot water is left at room temperature and allowed to cool down. In this experiment, we will explore how to measure the change in entropy of the universe during a cooling experiment. And calculate the free energy change for the water in the cooling process.

Before learning how to do the experiment and gather data, let's learn some laws and equations that allow us to calculate temperature change and increase in entropy during cooling experiments. Newton's Law of Cooling states that the rate of temperature change of an object is proportional to the difference between its own temperature and the temperature of the surroundings.

$$\frac{dT}{dt} \propto (T_s - T)$$

Where T is the temperature of the object, T_s is the temperature of the surroundings. Using calculus, this relationship can be converted into this equation,

$$T(t) = T_s + (T_0 - T_s)e^{-kt}$$

where lower case t represents time, T_s denotes temperature of the surroundings, T_0 is the initial temperature of the object, $T(t)$ is the temperature of the object at time t, and k is a constant that depends on the characteristics of the object and its surroundings.

Using this equation, one can calculate the temperature of a cooling system at any time if all the other variables are known. This equation also shows that temperature is an exponential function of time. Thus, when a hot object, like a glass of hot water, is placed in a cooler environment, its temperature will decrease at an exponential rate until it reaches the temperature of the surroundings.

Entropy is a "state property," which is a quantity that depends only upon the current state of the system. Quantities that are state properties do not depend on the path by which the system arrived at its present state. Therefore, the most useful way to quantify a state property is to measure its change.

Now, let's see how to calculate the change in entropy, or ΔS . When talking about entropy, we must first define the system. In this experiment, the system is the water, the surroundings are the air in the room. So the change in entropy of the universe, or $\Delta S_{\text{universe}}$ is a sum of the change in entropies of these individual components, assuming there is only energy exchange between water and air.

$$\Delta S_{\text{universe}} = \Delta S_{\text{water}} + \Delta S_{\text{air}}$$

Mathematically, the change in entropy is defined as heat gained or lost, denoted by q, divided by the temperature, T, in Kelvin.

$$\Delta S = \frac{q}{T}$$

This equation can be applied to both the water and the air. When using this equation for water, then q is the heat lost by water and T is the temperature of water in Kelvin. When using this equation for air, then q is the heat gained by air and T is the temperature of air in Kelvin. We know that the hot water will cool spontaneously to the surrounding temperature. Heat leaves water, or q has a negative sign for water, thus ΔS_{water} is negative. Entropy of water decreases. On the contrary, the surrounding air gains heat or q has a positive sign for air. Therefore, ΔS_{air} is positive. Entropy of the air increases. From the second law of the thermodynamics, we know that the change in entropy of the universe must be positive for a spontaneous process. We will calculate the $\Delta S_{\text{universe}}$ at various recorded temperatures.

In this experiment, we will test these theoretical predictions of Newton's Law of Cooling and the second law of thermodynamics.

Procedures:

1. Hold the thermometer in the air for 2 minutes, or until the reading is stable. Record the temperature as the temperature of the air in **data table 1**. (1 point)
2. Fill a small cooking pot with between 500 mL to 1000 mL of water. Record the mL of water used in **data table 1** (1 point)
3. Place the cooking pot with water on a stove and heat the water to boiling. Once the water boils, turn off the stove.
4. Carefully remove the cooking pot from the stove, and place it on the table on top of few layers of paper towels. The paper towels will act as insulation between the water and the cool table. That makes the universe consists of only two parts, the water and the air. Measure the temperature of the water using the thermometer. Record the temperature as the temperate of water at 0'00''
5. Start the stopwatch and record the temperature of the water every minute for the first 20 minutes in **data table-1**. (1 point)
6. For the next 20 minutes, record the temperature every 5 minutes in **data table-1**. (1 point)
7. For the rest of the time, record the temperature every 10 minutes in **data table-1**. (1 point)
8. Stop taking measurements when the water has come close to room temperature measured in step 1.
9. Calculate the temperature change, ΔT for water for the first time-interval by subtracting the temperature of water at 0'00'' (0 minute 0 second) from that at 1'00'', record ΔT as the temperature change at 0'00''.
10. Calculate the ΔT for the rest of time intervals.
11. Using $q = (\text{mass of water in grams}) \times \frac{4.18 \text{ J}}{\text{g} \cdot ^\circ\text{C}} \times \Delta T$ to calculate q of water. Record it in **data table 1**.
12. Using $q_{\text{air}} = -q_{\text{water}}$ to calculate the q for the air and record it in **data table 1**. (2 point)
13. Using $\Delta S = \frac{q_{\text{water}}}{T}$ to calculate the ΔS for water, make sure convert the temperature of water to Kelvins and record it in **data table 1**. T is the temperature of the water. (1 point)
14. Using $\Delta S = \frac{q_{\text{air}}}{T}$ to calculate the ΔS for air, make sure convert the temperature of water to Kelvins and record it in **data table 1**. T is the temperature of the air. (1 point)
15. Using $\Delta S_{\text{universe}} = \Delta S_{\text{water}} + \Delta S_{\text{air}}$ to calculate the ΔS of the universe and record it in **data table 1**. (1 point)
16. Using $\Delta G_{\text{water}} = -T\Delta S_{\text{universe}}$ to calculate the free energy change for water, and record it in **data table 1**. T is the temperature of water. (1 point)
17. Manipulate the Newton law of cooling,

$$T(t) = T_s + (T_0 - T_s)e^{-kt}$$

$$\text{We get } \ln\left(\frac{T(t)-T_s}{T_0-T_s}\right) = -kt$$

18. Calculate $\ln\left(\frac{T(t)-T_s}{T_0-T_s}\right)$ at various time, t , and record it in **data table 1**. (1 point)
19. Plot $\ln\left(\frac{T(t)-T_s}{T_0-T_s}\right)$ vs time, the slope is $-k$
20. Use the k from step 19 and Newton's law of cooling, $T(t) = T_s + (T_0 - T_s)e^{-kt}$ to calculate the predicated $T(t)$ at various time, t and record it in **data table 1**. (2 point)
21. Then, plot the measure temperature $T(t)$ from data table 1, and the predicted $T(t)$ from step 20 vs time, t , in minutes in the same graph. Attach the graph to your lab report. (1 point)
22. Plot $\Delta S_{\text{universe}}$, ΔS_{water} and ΔS_{air} vs time, t , in the same graph. Attach the graph to your lab report. (1 point)
23. Plot ΔG_{water} vs time, t . Attach the graph to your lab report. (1 point)
24. All the graph must have the corresponding title, name of the axis. Try use excel to do all the calculations.

EXPERIMENT
EIGHT

EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANT DETERMINATION
AIM:

To determine the equilibrium constant for the given reaction at atmospheric pressure and temperature.

APPARATUS: 500ml beaker, measuring jar, conical flask, burette, pipette, heating mantle, thermometers, specific gravity bottles

CHEMICALS REQUIRED: Distill water, $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$, CCl_4 , KI, starch indicator

THEORY:

According to the distribution law, "A solid or liquid distributes itself between two immiscible solvents in such a way that the ratio of its concentrations in the both solvents is constant" provided

1. The temperature remains constant.
2. The substance dissolves in both the solvents in the same form.
3. No chemical combination takes place between the solute and either of the solvents.
4. The concentration of the solute is low.

The ratio of concentration in the two solvents is called the partition co-efficient or distribution co-efficient. However the distribution law doesn't hold good in the distribution of iodine between CCl_4 and aqueous KI. This is due to the formation of iodine complex KI_3 in the aqueous KI. But if the concentration of free iodine is taken into the consideration the distribution law might hold good. The total concentration of iodine in the aqueous layer is given by

$$\text{Total concentration of iodine} = \text{Cl}_2 = \text{Cl}_2(\text{free}) + \text{Cl}_3$$

This concentration of I_2 is determined by titrating with standard $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ solution. Similarly, the concentrations of I_2 in organic layer can also be determined by titrating with standard $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$.

$$\left(\frac{\text{Concentration of free iodine}}{\text{in aqueous layer}} \right) = \left(\frac{\text{Concentration of iodine in organic layer}}{\text{partition co-efficient}} \right)$$

Then the value of Cl_3 is calculated, provided the initial concentration is known.

Knowing the values of Cl_3 , Cl_2 , Cl the equilibrium constant is calculated using the formula.

$$K = \frac{Cl_3}{Cl_2 \cdot Cl}$$

Let

The concentration of iodine in organic layer = C_1 mol lit⁻¹

The concentration of iodine in aqueous layer = C_2 mol lit⁻¹

Partition co-efficient of iodine between organic layer and aqueous layer = K_o { let $K_o = 83.18$ }

Concentration of free iodine in aqueous layer = C_1/K_o mol lit⁻¹

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Concentration of KI}_3 \text{ (formed)} &= \left(\text{Total I}_2 \text{ concentration in aqueous layer} \right) - \left(\text{Free I}_2 \text{ concentration} \right) \\ &= C_2 - \left(\frac{C_1}{K_o} \right) \text{ mol. lit}^1 \end{aligned}$$

Since one mole of I_3 is formed from one mole of the I, the concentration of free KI at equilibrium is given as $C_3 - \left[C_2 - \left(\frac{C_1}{K_o} \right) \right]$ mol. Lit⁻¹

Where

C_3 is initial concentration of I.

The equilibrium concentration is given by the relation

$$K = \frac{\left[C_2 - \left(\frac{C_1}{K_o} \right) \right]}{\left(\frac{C_1}{K_o} \right) \left\{ C_3 - \left[C_2 - \left(\frac{C_1}{K_o} \right) \right] \right\}}$$

SOLUTIONS TO BE PREPARED:

1. 0.1 M KI of 250 ml solution
2. 0.15 M KI of 100ml and 0.2 M KI of 100ml solution from 0.1 M KI solution.
3. 1% Iodine in CCl_4
4. 0.1 M $Na_2S_2O_3$ 500ml solution
5. 1 % starch indicator solution.

1. 0.1M KI of 250 ml solution

- Weigh the quantity of KI required to prepare 250 ml solution.
- Dissolve in 50 ml distill water and transfer it to a 250 ml standard flask using funnel.
- Add distill water till meniscus of the standard flask.

2. 0.15M KI of 100 ml solution & 0.2 M KI of 100 ml solution

- Calculate the volume of 0.1 M KI solution required to prepare 0.15 M 100 ml KI solution.
- To the obtained volume calculate the weight of KI required to prepare the solution.
- Add the quantity of KI to 50 ml distill water and transfer it to the required standard flask.
- Add distill water till the meniscus of the standard flask.
- In the same procedure prepare the 0.2 M KI solution from 0.1 M KI solution.

3. 1 % Iodine in CCl₄

- This is same as 10 ml saturated I₂ in CCl₄.
- Weigh 1 gm of Iodine and place it in a 100 ml beaker
- Add 10 ml of CCl₄ and stir it thoroughly.
- Decant the solution into a 100 ml standard flask leaving undissolved solid Iodine.
- Again, add another 10 ml of CCl₄ to the undissolved solid Iodine.
- Again, decant the solution into the standard flask.
- Repeat the process, until the solution is upto the mark of 100 ml of standard flask.

4. 0.1 N Na₂S₂O₃ 500ml solution

- Molecular weight of Sodium Thiosulphate is 248.
- By using Normality formula find out the weight of Thiosulphate required for 500 ml solution preparation.
- Add the Thiosulphate to 50 ml of distill water and transfer it to 500ml standard flask using funnel.
- Add the distill water till the meniscus of the standard flask.

5. Starch Indicator solution preparation

- Weigh 1 gm of starch powder
- Dissolve 1 gm in 50 ml of distill water.
- Transfer the solution to 100 ml standard flask using funnel.
- Add Distill water till the meniscus of the standard flask.

PROCEDURE:

Prepare 250 ml of M/10 KI solution. From this solution, prepare 100 ml of M/15 KI and 100 ml of M/20 KI solutions. Then take 100 ml of M/10 KI solution and 10 ml of saturated I₂ in CCl₄ solution in bottle A.

In bottle B pipette out 100 ml of M/15 KI solution, 7.5 ml of saturated I₂ in CCl₄ solution and 2.5 ml of CCl₄ solution.

In bottle C pipette out 100 ml of M/20 KI solution and 5 ml of CCl₄ solution, 5 ml of saturated I₂ in CCl₄ solution.

The bottles should be kept in a water bath at ambient temperature and pressure for about 30 min with periodic shaking of bottles.

After 30 min, the organic layer and aqueous layer obtained in each bottle were measured using a measuring jar.

BOTTLE A:

- Measure the volume of organic and aqueous layers in the bottle
- Entire amount of organic layer is titrated against standard $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ solution using standard procedure.
- Entire amount of aqueous layer is titrated against standard $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ solution using standard procedure.
- The titration values are noted. The above procedure is repeated for the other two bottles.
- Readings were tabulated and equilibrium constants were calculated.

Observation table 1:

S.No.	Bottle	Volume of organic layer (ml)	Volume of aqueous layer (ml)

Observation table 2:

S.No.	Bottle	Volume of organic layer (ml)	Burette Readings		Volume of Thiosulphate solution consumed (ml)
			Initial	Final	

Observation table 2:

S.No.	Bottle	Volume of aqueous layer (ml)	Burette Readings	Volume of Thiosulphate solution consumed (ml)

RESULT:

The equilibrium constant for the given reaction at atmospheric temperature and pressure is found to be _____ mol. lit⁻¹.

EXPERIMENT**NINE**

JOULE'S EXPERIMENT AND THE FIRST LAW OF THERMODYNAMICS

(Virtual Experiment)

AIM:

To validate the First Law of Thermodynamics using Joule's Experiment

APPARATUS:

Heating vessel, Thermometer, Agitator

CHEMICALS REQUIRED:

Water

THEORY & PRINCIPLE:

Joule's experiment demonstrated the validity of the first law of thermodynamics. Electrical or mechanical energy can be converted into thermal energy, but the total amount of energy is conserved. In this Demonstration, the amount of heat Q in joules generated in a circuit element of resistance R (immersion heater) is measured by a calorimeter.

Assume that all the heat is absorbed by the water and measure the temperature increase from t_0 to t . Then

$$Q = m c \Delta t = \rho \pi r_1^2 h 10^{-6} c (t - t_0).$$

Joule's law gives Q liberated by current I flowing through a resistor with resistance R for a time T ,

$$Q = I^2 R T.$$

Using Ohm's Law $I = E/R$, we obtain $I^2 R T = E^2 T/R$; therefore

$$\rho \pi r_1^2 h 10^{-6} c (t - t_0) = E^2 T/R,$$

$$t = \frac{E^2 T}{\rho \pi r_1^2 h 10^{-6} c R} + t_0.$$

The final temperature t (in °C) and the energy gained by the water Q (in J) are shown on the diagram.

EXPERIMENT**TEN**

AIM:

To Understand how $\Delta G = \Delta H_{\text{sys}} - T\Delta S_{\text{sys}}$ expressed the second law of thermodynamics by exploring energy transfer between system and its surroundings.

APPARATUS:

Thermometer, 100ml measuring jar, 150 ml beakers -3, stirring rod, digital thermometer, 10 ml measuring jar

CHEMICALS REQUIRED:

Ammonium Chloride/ Ammonium Nitrate, Calcium Chloride, Acetone

Objective-1: Defining Enthalpy and Looking at Entropy Changes in the Surroundings**Case one for enthalpy**

1. Measure out 100 mL of water in a clean 150-mL beaker. Once again, label the “system” and the “surroundings” in the diagram below.
2. Place the beaker on your paper in the region labeled “system” below, then measure the temperature of its contents with a thermometer and record.
3. Add 5.0 g of ammonium chloride or ammonium nitrate.
4. While holding the beaker at its base, stir, and make and record your observations, including the final temperature of the mixture.
5. Your hand at the base of the beaker can be considered part of the surroundings. Was thermal energy transferred to your hand from the beaker, or away from your hand to the beaker? Since my hand feels cooler, thermal energy is being transferred from my hand to the beaker.
6. Label the diagram below with an arrow, showing the direction of the transfer of thermal energy. Is thermal energy transferred from the surroundings to the system or from the system to the surroundings?
7. Is the change endothermic or exothermic?
8. Is ΔH of the system positive or negative?

Case two for enthalpy:

1. Measure 100 mL of water in a clean 150-mL beaker.

2. Place the beaker in the “system” below, and measure and record the temperature of its contents. Add 5.0 g of calcium chloride.
3. While holding the beaker at its base, stir, and make and record your observations, including the final temperature of the mixture.
4. Was thermal energy transferred to your hand from the beaker, or away from your hand to the beaker? Since my hand feels warmer, thermal energy is being transferred from the beaker to my hand.
5. Label the diagram below with an arrow, showing the direction of the transfer of thermal energy. Is thermal energy transferred from the surroundings to the system or from the system to the surroundings?
6. Is the change endothermic or exothermic?
7. Is ΔH of the system positive or negative?

EXPERIMENT**ELEVEN**

USING THE IDEAL GAS LAW TO DETERMINE THE PURITY OF A ZINC SAMPLE**AIM:**

1. Generate and collect hydrogen gas over water by the reaction of zinc metal with HCl (aq).
2. Determine the percent purity of zinc sample combining the ideal gas law with stoichiometry.

APPARATUS:

Heating vessel, Thermometer, Agitator

CHEMICALS REQUIRED:

Water

THEORY & PRINCIPLE:

An ideal gas follows the ideal gas law at all conditions of P and T. The particles in an ideal gas do not have finite size and volume. The collisions between the ideal gas particles are said to be elastic, they exert no attractive or repulsive forces. Hydrogen gas generated in today's experiment is, however, a real gas not an ideal gas. Real gases consist of molecules of finite size, which exert forces on each other. A gas will act like an ideal gas if its gas molecules are small, when the pressure is low, and the temperature is high. For our experimental conditions today, we can assume that hydrogen gas adheres to the ideal gas law.

Today's experiment is an example of a single replacement reaction. It involves the measurement of the volume of hydrogen gas generated from a reaction of zinc with excess hydrochloric acid

The hydrogen gas produced will be collected over water in a buret. This results in a gas sample that is a mixture of hydrogen gas and water vapor inside the buret. To determine the pressure of hydrogen gas alone, you will need to use Dalton's Law of Partial Pressures. In accordance with Dalton's Law, the atmospheric pressure (P_T) is equal to the sum of the pressures of hydrogen gas (P_H) and the vapor pressure of water (P_W):

$$P_T = P_H + P_W$$

Equation 2

P_{H_2} = partial pressure of hydrogen gas = $P_A - P_W$

P_{H_2} is in atm or mmHg. Use the appropriate R value in **equation 5**.

P_T = atmospheric pressure provided by your instructor

P_W = vapor pressure of water at temperature T

V = volume in L

n_{H_2} = moles of hydrogen gas evolved

R = Ideal gas constant, 0.08206

R = Ideal gas constant, 62.36

T = Temperature in Kelvin ($^{\circ}\text{C} + 273$)

The grams of zinc present in the impure sample can be determined by using the calculated the moles from equation 4.

Gram of Zn reacted = ____ mol H_2 x ____ g Zn **Equation 6**

Finally determine the percent purity of the zinc sample by dividing the mass of zinc reacted by the mass of the impure sample and multiplying by 100%.

% Zn in the Sample = x 100%

Equation 7

Table 1. Vapor Pressure of Water at different Temperatures

Temperature (°C)	Vapor Pressure (mm Hg)	Temperature (°C)	Vapor Pressure (mm Hg)
16.0	13.6	24.0	22.4
17.0	14.5	25.0	23.8
18.0	15.5	26.0	25.2
19.0	16.5	27.0	26.7
20.0	17.5	28.0	28.3
21.0	18.6	29.0	30.0
22.0	19.8	30.0	31.8
23.0	21.1	31.0	33.7

PROCEDURE:

1. Add distilled water through the funnel until the water level is just below the 0.0 mL mark in the burette.
2. Raise and lower the funnel to help expel any air bubbles. (It is important that no air bubbles remain in the tubing or funnel stem at the beginning of the experiment.)
3. You may have to adjust the height of the funnel relative to the rest of the apparatus. Be very careful during this process so that water does not flow through the rubber tubing used to connect the large test tube to the burette.
4. Take a large test tube in a 150 mL beaker. Use a spatula to add between **0.100 g - 0.110 g** of zinc powder into the large test tube.

5. Record the mass of the zinc in your **DATA TABLE**. Add about 2.0 mL of 6.0 M HCl into a small test tube (70 mm x 10 mm).
6. Using a forceps, gently slide the small test tube and contents into the larger test tube containing the zinc powder.
7. The small test tube should be in the vertical position (mouth pointing upwards). You should be very careful so that none of the HCl comes in contact with the zinc.
8. If any of the HCl comes in contact with the zinc, you will have to start the experiment all over again.
9. Connect the large test tube to the apparatus while keeping the small test tube containing the HCl in the vertical position.
10. Move the funnel either up or down so that the water in the funnel and the burette are at the same level.
11. This equalizes the pressure of the gases trapped inside the buret with the atmospheric pressure.
12. Record the volume of water in the burette to the nearest 0.01 mL as your initial burette reading in the **DATA TABLE**.
13. Always read your volume measure from the top down. Measure the temperature of the water in the funnel using a thermometer.
14. Hold the thermometer in the funnel containing water until the temperature is stabilized.
15. Record the temperature to one decimal place in the **DATA TABLE**. Record the atmospheric pressure (P_T) in the DATA TABLE.
16. Carefully read through the rest of the procedure before continuing. This portion of the procedure must be carried out by you and your partner in a coordinated manner.
17. If any part of this is unclear, please consult your instructor. The reaction between 6.0 M HCl and zinc occurs rapidly after mixing.

18. One student will be responsible for mixing the zinc and the 6.0 M HCl in the test tubes and the other student will be required to lower the funnel so that the level of water in the funnel is at the same height as the level of water in the burette during the time the hydrogen gas is generated.
19. If you are not sure about what you should do, please consult your instructor before you proceed to the next step.
20. With one student ready to lower the funnel, the other student should gently incline the large test tube so that a portion of the HCl in the small test tube will run out of the small test tube and come in contact with the zinc powder in the large test tube.
21. Be careful not to allow any of the HCl to flow through the rubber tubing connecting the large test tube and the burette.
22. The student responsible for lowering the funnel must do so, when necessary, after the HCl and zinc have been mixed so that the level of water in the funnel is at the same height as the level of water in the burette.
23. Once the reaction has subsided, gently incline the test tube again so that more HCl comes in contact with the zinc.
24. After all the hydrogen gas has evolved, the level of water in the burette will remain constant.
25. At this point you should not observe any unreacted zinc. Adjust the height of the funnel so that the level of water in the funnel is at the same height as the level of water in the burette.
26. Record the final burette reading in your **DATA TABLE**. The volume of hydrogen gas produced is the difference between the final and initial burette readings.
27. Pour the contents of the large test tube into a labeled waste container in the hood. Remove the small test tube with forceps.
28. Wash the large and small test tubes with soap and water followed by rinsing with distilled water.

29. Place the large test tubes in the tray and the small test tubes in a 400 mL beaker found next to the oven.
30. Do a complete set of calculations on the data from run 1.
31. Show the % zinc in the sample to your instructor and then proceed with runs 2 and 3.
32. For each run use a clean, dry set of glass tubes from the side bench. Record your results.
33. Use your data to calculate the percent purity of zinc.

DATA TABLE (3 pts.)

Quantity	Run 1	Run 2	Run 3
Water temperature (T)			
Atmospheric pressure (P_T)			
Vapor pressure of water (P_W) from Table 1			
Partial pressure of H_2 (P)			
Mass of impure Zn sample used			
Final burette reading (mL)			
Initial burette reading (mL)			
Volume of H_2 gas (V_H) (mL)			
Volume of H_2 gas (V_H) (L)			

1. Use the ideal gas law (See **equation 5.**) and data from the table on the previous page to calculate the moles of hydrogen gas. Show the calculation setups for Run 1 with units in place below. Be sure to report your answers to the correct number of significant figures in the appropriate box. (3 pts.)

Quantity	Run 1	Run 2	Run 3
----------	-------	-------	-------

Moles of H₂ gas evolved

2. Solve stoichiometry problem (See **equation 6.**) to determine the grams of zinc reacted. Show the calculation setups for Run 1 with units in place below. Be sure to report your answers to the correct number of significant figures in the appropriate box. (2 pts.)

Quantity	Run 1	Run 2	Run 3
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Grams of zinc reacted

3. Calculate the percent purity of the zinc sample (See **equation 7.**). Show the calculation setups for Run 1 with units in space below. Be sure to report your answers to the correct number of significant figures in the appropriate box. (2 pts.)

Run 1	Run 2	Run 3
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% zinc in the sample

EXPERIMENT**TWELVE**

HEAT, TEMPERATURE AND CONDUCTION**LAB ACTIVITY:**

All things are made of atoms and molecules which are always in motion. When they are heated, they move faster and when they are cooled, they move slower. For example, if you put a room-temperature metal spoon into a hot liquid like soup or hot chocolate, the metal gets hotter. But what actually has to happen for the hot liquid to make the metal hotter: how do the atoms and molecules actually get heated and cooled?

To answer this question, you really have to think about the moving atoms and molecules as having energy. Anything that has mass and is moving, like a train, a moving ball, or an atom has a certain amount of energy. The energy of a moving object is called kinetic energy. If the speed of the object increases, its kinetic energy increases. If the speed of the object decreases, its kinetic energy decreases. So if the atoms or molecules of a substance are moving fast, they have more kinetic energy than when they are moving more slowly. In the example of a spoon in hot liquid, the molecules of hot liquid are moving quickly so they have a lot of kinetic energy. When the room-temperature spoon is placed in the liquid, the fast moving molecules in the liquid contact the slower moving atoms in the spoon. The fast-moving molecules hit the slower-moving atoms and speed them up. In this way, the fast-moving molecules transfer some of their kinetic energy to the slower atoms so that these slower atoms now have more kinetic energy. This process of transferring energy by direct contact is called conduction.

Cool spoon to warmer liquid

Student Sheet 2

Cooling things by conduction works the same way as warming. This time, a hot metal spoon is put in room-temperature water. The faster-moving atoms in the spoon contact the slower-moving molecules in the water. The atoms in the spoon transfer some of their energy to the molecules in the water. The spoon will get cooler and the water will get a little warmer.

Hot spoon to cooler liquid

Another example is cans of room-temperature soda pop placed in a cooler filled with ice. Energy is transferred from the warmer metal can to the cooler ice making the can colder. Energy is then transferred from the warmer soda to the colder can. This transfer of energy from the soda results in decreased motion of the molecules of the soda, which can be measured as a lower temperature and colder soda. The way to cool by something by conduction is for its energy to be transferred to something colder. Energy can only be transferred from something at a higher temperature to something at a lower temperature; it can't cool something by adding "coldness" to it. A substance can only be made colder by allowing its energy to be transferred to something colder.

Student Sheet 3

When speaking about temperature and heat it is important to understand what they are and how they are different. Temperature is a measure of the average kinetic energy of the atoms or molecules of a substance. It is commonly indicated in degrees ($^{\circ}\text{C}/^{\circ}\text{F}$). It is the measurement of the intensity of heat energy. By taking the temperature of something, you are actually getting information about the kinetic energy of its atoms and molecules, but not the kinetic energy of any particular one atom. There are more than a billion trillion atoms or molecules, in even a small sample of a substance that are constantly moving and bumping into each other and transferring little amounts of energy. So at any time, the atoms and molecules don't all have the same kinetic energy. Some are moving faster and some are moving slower than others, but most are about the same.

Heat is the amount of kinetic energy that is transferred from a substance at a higher temperature to a substance at a lower temperature and is another word for thermal energy. Heat is measured in joules. The scientific meaning of heat has to do with energy that is being transferred. During conduction, the energy transferred from faster-moving atoms to slower-moving atoms is called heat and actually causes temperature changes.

DATA TABLE 1: Room-temperature washers placed in hot water

TEMPERATURE OF.....	BEFORE	AFTER
Water in your cup		
Water in control cup		
Washers		

ANALYSIS:

Complete the following questions in on notebook paper.

1. Explain, on the molecular level, how energy was transferred from the hot water to the room-temperature spoon
2. How did the temperature of the washers and water change in both parts of the activity?
3. Knowing what you do about heating and cooling atoms and molecules, why do you think the temperature changed?

4. Describe how the process of conduction caused the temperature of the washers and water to change in the activity.
5. Draw what the set-up looked like. Include motion lines to the "Before" and "After" illustration below and add descriptive words like "warmer" or "cooler" to describe the change in temperature of the water and the washers.
6. Explain how the motion of the atoms or molecules of a substance affect the temperature of the substance?
7. What is conduction?
8. Explain the difference and the relationship between heat and temperature.
9. Develop an activity where a hot metal object is placed in a container of room temperature water.

Identify the tools you would need.

Write out the steps you will need to take and why.

Draw a diagram of the activity

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